

***Ortho*-Amido-phenylhydrazine and some
Interesting Heterocyclic Compounds
derived from it.**

BY
PRAPHULLA CHANDRA GUHA
AND
SUDHANYA KUMAR RAY.

Although *m*-amido- and *p*-amido-phenylhydrazines and a good number of compounds derived from them are known (Bischler and Brodsky, *Ber.*, 22, 2810; Griess, *Ber.*, 18, 963; Freund, *Ber.*, 16, 1320), no systematic investigation has been carried out with *o*-amido-phenylhydrazine, it being itself unknown. Bischler (*Ber.*, 22, 240) describes a method for the preparation of *o*-amido-phenylhydrazine, but there is no mention of its melting point, method of separation and purification, nor does he give any analytical results of his compound. The natural conclusion to be drawn from the work of Bischler is that he merely got some indication of the formation of this compound, but he could not actually isolate it.

Reference should be made here to the works of Hempell (*J. pr. Chem.*, 41, 170) and of Nietzki (*Ber.*, 22, 3221). The former prepared the methyl derivative of *o*-amido-phenylhydrazine from *o*-nitro-methylaniline by the action of nitrous acid and then reducing the nitroso derivative so formed, whilst Nietzki prepared *o*-amido-phenylhydrazine sulphonic acid from *o*-nitraniline sulphonic acid in the usual manner. Franzen (*Ber.*, 40,

909) obtained the benzal derivative of *o*-amido-phenylhydrazine by reducing the benzal compound of *o*-nitro-phenylhydrazine with sodium bisulphite and effected the ring closure of his amido-hydrazine derivative by two per cent. hydrochloric acid and steam.

o-Amido-phenylhydrazine has now been prepared by reducing *o*-nitro-phenylhydrazine with stannous chloride and hydrochloric acid. The success of the method depends on the concentration of the hydrochloride solution in the absence of air and precipitating it with ether from an alcoholic solution.

Both the amino and hydrazino groups react with phenyl mustard oil forming 1-phenylthiocarbamido-phenyl 4-phenyl-thiosemicarbazide $\text{PhNH.CS.NH.C}_6\text{H}_4.\text{NH.NH.CS.NHPh}$ (I). An analogous compound has also been obtained from *o*-tolyl mustard oil. Benzaldehyde gives a dibenzylidene derivative $\text{PhCH:N.C}_6\text{H}_4.\text{NHN:CHPh}$ (II).

With potassium ethylxanthate it gives a compound of the empirical formula $\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{N}_3\text{S}$ which may represent either the benzotriazine compound (A) or the benzodiazole compound (B) as shown below :

Both of these formulae contain a thiol or mercaptanic group. A compound of the formula (B) should readily

form a hydrochloride and react with benzaldehyde to form a benzal derivative, whereas a compound of the formula (A) should be acidic in nature and should not form a hydrochloride or a benzal derivative (Compare Guha and De, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1215; Arndt and Bielich, *Ber.*, 56, 809). The compound $C_7H_7N_3S$ is found to be acidic in nature and to form alkali salts, a yellow mercaptide with mercuric chloride, a disulphide and a benzoyl derivative showing the presence of a mercaptanic group, and being in agreement with the benzothiozine formula (A) for the compound.

Urea condenses with amido-phenylhydrazine to form benzo-keto-tetrahydrotriazine (IV), while glyoxal sodium bisulphite reacts to form a benzo-hepta-triazine compound (V), thus:

the latter being basic, combines with one molecule of sulphurous acid (Compare Cain, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 105, 1441).

o-Nitrophenylhydrazine (*Ber.*, 22, 2801) reacts with thiocarbamides in the normal way giving *o*-nitrophenyl-thiosemicarbazides. When these thiosemicarbazides are reduced with tin and hydrochloric acid, the reaction proceeds in two distinct stages. First, the nitro group is reduced to the corresponding amino derivative (VI), which again in presence of hydrochloric acid

loses a molecule of ammonia to yield a benzo-thiodiazine derivative, thus :

The same benzo-thiodiazine compound (m. p. 151°) was also obtained when the amino compound (m. p. 253°) was treated with acetic anhydride.

The thiodiazine constitution given above follows from the fact that it is insoluble in alkali and does not give any mercaptide or thioether or disulphide.

The benzal derivative of *o*-nitro-phenylhydrazine yields on reduction with tin and hydrochloric acid, phenylbenziminazole hydrochloride from which the base can be liberated by ammonia, thus:—

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of o-Amido-phenylhydrazine hydrochloride.

A mixture of 10 gms. of *o*-nitrophenylhydrazine hydrochloride, 45 gms. of stannous chloride, 60 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid and a little water was taken in

a stoppered bottle and shaken vigorously for 2-3 hours in a shaking machine, when the reduction was complete. The mixture became hot and dark in colour. The contents were then diluted with 600-700 cc of water, warmed and tin removed by hydrogen sulphide. The largely diluted solution acquired a brownish red colour on exposure to air, and the concentration was therefore carried out under vacuum in the absence of air as far as practicable.

The fairly concentrated solution on cooling gave crystals which were slightly brownish in colour. It was purified by precipitating by ether from an alcoholic solution as a white powder and was dried in a vacuum desiccator. M. p. 263-265° with decomposition. Yield 3-4 gms.

(Found: N=21.18. $C_6H_5N_3 \cdot 2HCl$ requires N=21.42 per cent).

The Free Base: o-Amido-phenylhydrazine.—The free base was obtained by adding ammonia or sodium acetate to the hot concentrated aqueous solution of the hydrochloride, as a reddish brown amorphous mass. It was filtered and crystallised from dilute alcohol avoiding the presence of air as much as possible, in contact with which it soon gets coloured brownish black. It dissolved in acids and melted between 295-302° with decomposition showing it to be rather impure.

o-Amido-phenylhydrazine and Phenyl Mustard Oil: Formation of 4-Phenyl-1-ortho-phenyl-thiocarbamido-phenyl-thiosemicarbazide, $C_6H_4(NH.CS.NHPh)NH.NH.CS.NHPh$ (I).

An alcoholic solution of 2 gms of *o*-amido-phenylhydrazine hydrochloride (1 mol) and 1.4 gms of phenyl

mustard oil (1 mol) was heated on a water-bath under reflux for 2-3 hours. The reaction product was then poured into water, when a white solid separated out. This was crystallised from dilute alcohol in shining white rectangular plates, which melted at 80° and was soluble in hot water and in cold concentrated alkali. Yield 1.1 gm.

(Found: S=16.02 $C_{20}H_{19}N_5S_2$ requires S=16.29 per cent)

o-Amido-phenylhydrazine and *o*-Tolyl Mustard Oil:
Formation of 4-Tolyl-1-tolyl-thiocarbamido-phenyl-thio-
semicarbazide

The method of preparation was the same as in the case of the preceding compound. Yield 0.7 gm from 0.5 gm of *o*-amido-phenylhydrazine hydrochloride and 0.4 gm of *o*-tolyl mustard oil. M. p. $282^{\circ}C$

(Found: S=15.8 $C_{27}H_{23}N_5S_2$ requires S=15.2 per cent)

Dibenzylidene Derivative of o-Amidophenyl-hydra-
zine (II)

A dilute alcoholic solution of 0.8 gm of *o*-amido-phenylhydrazine hydrochloride and 0.6 gm of benzaldehyde was heated on a water-bath under reflux for about 2 hours. Some alcohol was then distilled off and on adding water to the residue a white solid separated out. Any unconverted benzaldehyde was removed by passing steam through the solution. On concentration and cooling a white substance came down; this was dissolved in the minimum quantity of hot water and obtained as a white amorphous powder on scratching the sides of the vessel.

M. p. 206-207°. It was the hydrochloride of a base and gave silver chloride with silver nitrate solution. (Found: N=10.95. $C_{20}H_{17}N_3.HCl.2H_2O$ requires N=11.30 per cent.). The free base was liberated from it as a white flocculent precipitate by boiling with ammonia.

o-Amido-phenylhydrazine and Potassium ethylxanthate: Formation of 2-Thio-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5:6-benzo-1:3:4-triazine (III).

A mixture of 1.2 gm. of *o*-amido-phenylhydrazine hydrochloride, 3 c.c. of alcoholic potash (1 c.c.=.12 gm. of KOH) and one gram of carbon bisulphide in alcoholic solution was heated on a water-bath for 6-7 hours under reflux. The reaction product was poured into water when a yellow precipitate came down, which was filtered off, washed with cold water and crystallised from hot water containing a few drops of hydrochloric acid. M.p. 298-300°. It was soluble in alcohol and in cold dilute alkali giving a deep yellowish brown solution and gave a beautiful blood-red colour with potassium ferricyanide.

(Found: N=24.95; S=19.81. $C_7H_7N_3S$ requires N=25.45; S=19.39 per cent.)

The *Benzoyl* derivative.—0.5 gm. of the benzo-triazine compound when benzoylated by Schotten-Baumann process gave about 0.3 gm. of a light yellow compound which when crystallised from alcohol melted at 174°.

The *disulphide* was prepared by adding iodine solution to an alcoholic solution of the benzo-triazine compound and then adding an excess of water when it was

completely precipitated as a yellow amorphous powder. It was washed with dilute potassium iodide, water and finally with alcohol and was found to be insoluble in all ordinary solvents. M.p. 208-210°.

*Urea and o-Amido-phenylhydrazine hydrochloride :
Formation of Benzo-keto-tetrahydrotriazine (IV).*

One gm. of *o*-amido-phenylhydrazine hydrochloride was intimately mixed with 0.6 gm. of urea in a dry clean mortar and the mixed powder was then heated in a dry boiling tube on an oil-bath to 135-145°C for about 2½ hours with occasional stirring. Ammonia evolved profusely and the contents became first semi-solid and after a while formed into a solid cake, when the evolution of ammonia ceased. The cake was carefully detached from the boiling tube, powdered and triturated with water, when a yellowish white powder was obtained which was crystallised from hot water (slightly acidulated with hydrochloric acid) in long rectangular plates. It melted at 310-312° and sublimed slowly at a higher temperature into mica-like plates. The substance was insoluble in acid but soluble in cold alkali.

(Found : N = 22.21. $C_7H_7ON_3 \cdot 2H_2O$ requires N = 22.58 per cent.)

*o-Amido-phenylhydrazine and Glyoxal : Formation
of a Benzo-hepta-triazine Compound (V).*

An aqueous solution of 1 gm. of *o*-amido-phenylhydrazine hydrochloride and 1.5 gm. of glyoxal sodium bisulphite was heated on a water-bath for half an hour. The colour changed from blue to yellow and the liquid became turbid. It was again heated for 2 hours over a

free flame when the colour changed to reddish brown and a solid mass began to separate out. It was allowed to cool, filtered and washed with water. The compound was insoluble in water, acids, alcohol, methyl alcohol, acetone and ether, difficultly soluble in alkali and highly soluble in pyridine. It could be crystallised from dilute pyridine with much difficulty and the crystals even then were not very well shaped. It melted at 212-214° with decomposition. The yield was 0.5 gm.

(Found : N=18.78. $C_8H_7N_3$, H_2SO_4 requires N=18.50 per cent.)

Reduction of 1-o-Nitrophenyl-4-phenyl-thiosemicarbazide: Formation of 1-o-Amido-phenyl-4-phenyl-thiosemicarbazide (VI) and 2-Phenylimino-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5:6-benzo-1:3:4-triazine (VII).

10 gms. of 1-o-nitrophenyl-4-phenyl-thiosemicarbazide, 10 gms. of granulated tin and 30 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid were heated on a water-bath for 3-4 hours in a flask fitted with an upright condenser. The contents of the flask were then diluted with about 500 c.c. of water and boiled till a pasty semi-solid mass which first formed went in solution. The tin was removed by hydrogen sulphide and the solution concentrated, and on cooling gave (i) white crystals of (VI). These were filtered off and the mother-liquor gave (ii) white curdy precipitate of (VII) on dilution with water.

The white crystalline mass (i) was purified by adding ether to an alcoholic solution of the substance, when it melted at 253-255° with decomposition. It was highly soluble in water and emitted the smell of phenyl-isocyanide when acted upon by nitrous acid. By diazotisation and coupling with β -naphthol, a red azo colour was

produced. The white substance on standing changed to reddish brown. Yield 1.5 gms.

(Found : N = 19.02. $C_{13}H_{14}N_4S$, HCl requires N = 18.96 per cent.)

The white curdy precipitate (ii) was crystallised from dilute alcohol: Yield 0.4 gms. M. p. 150-151°. It was insoluble in water and in alkali but soluble in strong hydrochloric acid. Evidently the hydrochloride is hydrolysed on dilution with water. The compound is feebly basic in nature.

(Found : N = 17.1. $C_{13}H_{11}N_3S$ requires N = 17.4 per cent.)

1-Amidophenyl-4-phenyl-thiosemicarbazide hydrochloride (VI) and Acetic Anhydride.—One gm. of 1-amidophenyl-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide hydrochloride was heated with 3-4 c.c. of acetic anhydride on a sand-bath till a clear solution was obtained. The reaction mixture was poured into cold water when a yellowish white crystalline mass separated out. A second crop was obtained by removing acetic acid by passing steam and evaporating the solution. M. p. 152°. It was insoluble in water and alkali.

o-Nitrophenylhydrazine and Allyl Mustard Oil: Formation of 1-o-Nitrophenyl-4-allylthiosemicarbazide.—An alcoholic solution of 2 gms. of *o*-nitro-phenylhydrazine and 1.5 gm. of allyl mustard oil was heated on a water-bath under reflux for about two hours. The product was poured into water, when yellow shining crystals separated out. These were filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from dilute alcohol. M. p. 164-165°. It was insoluble in water and in mineral acids but soluble in cold dilute alkali, producing a beautiful

bluish violet coloration which vanished on acidification. Yield 2.3 gm.

(Found: $N=22.47$ $C_{10}H_{12}O_2N_2S$ requires $N=22.22$ per cent.)

The benzaldehyde compound of *o*-nitrophenylhydrazine was prepared according to the method of Bischler (*loc. cit.*).

Reduction of the Benzal derivative of o-Nitrophenylhydrazine: Formation of μ -Phenylbenziminazole hydrochloride (VIII).

Three gms. of the benzal derivative were heated for 4-5 hours with an excess of tin and hydrochloric acid till a clear colourless solution was obtained, which on cooling gave white needle-shaped crystals. These were further purified by recrystallisation from water slightly acidified with hydrochloric acid. M. p. above 306° . Silver nitrate gave a white precipitate of silver chloride with its aqueous solution. Yield 2 gms.

(Found: $N=12.02$. $C_{13}H_{10}N_2$, HCl requires $N=12.13$ per cent.)

μ -Phenylbenziminazole.—On addition of ammonia to the aqueous solution of 0.3 gm. of the above hydrochloride, a white flocculent mass separated out. It was filtered off and washed with water. Yield 0.2 gm. M. p. $288-289^\circ$.

Salicylidene derivative of o-Nitrophenylhydrazine.—A mixture of 6 gm. of *o*-nitro-phenylhydrazine hydrochloride and 6 gm. of salicylaldehyde in dilute alcoholic solution was warmed and shaken. Brilliant crimson-red needle-shaped crystals separated out which were recrystallised from alcohol. M. p. 190° . The

yield was 1 gm. It was insoluble in water, soluble in cold dilute alkali and alcohol. It is a good dye for wool to which it imparts a beautiful orange-red colour from sulphuric acid bath.

(Found: N = 16.51 $C_{13}H_{12}O_3N_3$ requires N = 16.30 per cent.)

The *Benzoyl* derivative.—0.2 gm. of the above compound was benzoylated by Schotten-Baumann method, when a red solid mass separated which was crystallised from dilute alcohol. M. p. 140° . It was insoluble in alkali.

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CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY OF DACCA.

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